

HOMEROS project for natural hazards: An example from northern Peloponnese, Greece

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Background

Natural phenomena such as earthquakes, floods, and landslides, which appear throughout geological history, are now classified as natural hazards. These events pose significant risk to human safety on a global scale (Bathrellos and Skilodimou, 2006). Effective planning is essential for minimizing loss of life and reducing the economic impact of these hazards (Bathrellos *et al.*, 2024). Accurate information on the spatial distribution of natural hazards serves as a crucial resource for environmental planners and engineers, helping them identify suitable sites for land use and development (Bathrellos and Skilodimou, 2019).

Natural hazards are complex phenomena, and most published studies have focused on in-depth analyses of individual hazard types (Bathrellos *et al.*, 2016, Karpouza *et al.*, 2021, Skilodimou *et al.*, 2021, Youssef *et al.*, 2024). However, a particular area is rarely affected by only one hazard; instead, multiple hazards may occur simultaneously or consecutively. In such cases, managing separate hazard zones for each type of disaster becomes impractical, especially when multiple hazards must be considered (Bathrellos *et al.*, 2021, Karpouza *et al.*, 2023). The solution to this challenge lies in adopting a multi-hazard analysis, which allows for a comprehensive assessment of various hazard types. Multi-hazard analysis is an essential tool for selecting appropriate land uses and evaluating the vulnerability and risk of urban areas. It plays a critical role in mitigating natural hazards and managing urban disasters (Karpouza *et al.*, 2024).

Objectives

In this context, the HOMEROS project focuses on enhancing multi-hazard assessment approaches within the fields of seismology, geodesy, geology, geomorphology and engineering geology. It utilizes technical solutions tailored to the big data era, marking a major step forward in standardizing research methodologies, fostering collaboration, and improving the understanding and forecasting of natural hazards through Open Science practices. HOMEROS concentrates on high-hazard regions in Greece, characterized by intense seismic activity, floods, and landslides. It consolidates earthquake, ground deformation, flood, and landslide data to offer a comprehensive assessment of these hazards.

This paper provides data and results from the program related to flood events and the production of flood hazard assessment maps in the northern Peloponnese. This work represents an early example of the findings from the HOMEROS project, stemming from the collaboration between the University of Patras, Lund University, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, and the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens.

Study area

The study area includes the drainage basins of the Xerias, Phoenix, and Peneus rivers, located in the northern Peloponnese region of southern Greece (Fig. 1). The Xerias drainage basin spans 170 km² with a predominantly north-south elongated shape. Similarly, the Phoenix River basin covers around 94 km² and exhibits a southwest-to-northeast elongated orientation. Both river systems drain into the Gulf of Corinth. In contrast, the Peneus River drainage basin, occupying an area of approximately 900 km², extends in an east-west direction. It flows westward and discharges into the Ionian Sea (Fig. 1).

Methods

HOMEROS adopts an innovative approach by leveraging existing data and services from e-science gateways and platforms at multiple levels (national, research infrastructures, or scientific clusters), as well as external resources like Copernicus. It emphasizes the application of FAIR principles in research to deliver new open-access data products.

In this context, data from existing scientific publications were utilized to implement the project. Specifically, HOMEROS incorporated documented flood events that occurred for the period from 1920 to 2021, in the drainage basins of the Xerias, Phoenix, and Peneus rivers (Fig. 2), as reported by Bathrellos *et al.* (2017), Skilodimou *et al.* (2024) and Skilodimou *et al.* (2019), respectively. Additionally, it utilized information from these works concerning the applied methodologies and flood hazard assessment maps.

Figure 1. The study area comprises the drainage basins of the Xerias, Phoenix, and Peneus rivers.

Five key factors have been identified as the most significant in influencing flood events. These factors include slope, elevation, hydro-lithology, distance to streams, and land use. The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) was integrated with Geographic Information System (GIS) to facilitate the assessment of the chosen factors employed in the production of the flood hazard assessment maps.

Figure 2. Flood events in the drainage basins of the Xerias, Phoenix, and Peneus rivers.

Results

The recorded number of past flood events for each drainage basin is as follows: ten for the Xerias River, eleven for the Phoenix River, and eight for the Peneus River.

The flood hazard assessment maps for the three drainage basins were categorized into five levels of flood hazard: very low, low, moderate, high, and very high (Bathrellos *et al.*, 2016, Skilodimou *et al.*, 2021). As stated by Bathrellos *et al.* (2017), the northern and central regions of the Xerias drainage basin have the most extensive coverage of very high and high flood hazard zones. The moderate hazard zone is primarily located in the northeastern and central parts of the basin, whereas the low and very low hazard zones are concentrated in the southern region (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. The flood hazard assessment map in the drainage basin of the Xerias River.

The high and very high hazard zones are mainly located along the mainstream of the Xerias drainage network and at the points where it intersects with major tributaries. Notably, most of the recorded flood events in the study area occur within the very high and high flood hazard zones. The lowland terrain, gentle slopes, presence of impermeable formations, and urbanization of these areas contribute to increased surface runoff, creating conditions that are more prone to flooding.

According to Skilodimou *et al.* (2024), the very high and high flood hazard zones are mainly found in the northern and central parts of the Phoenix drainage basin, along the mainstream channel of the drainage network. The moderate hazard zone is largely concentrated in the central area, extending into the northern, western, and southern areas. In contrast, the southern, western, and eastern parts of the study area include many locations within the low and very low hazard zones (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. The flood hazard assessment map in the drainage basin of the Phoenix River.

The relatively small size of the Phoenix River drainage basin, along with its ephemeral streams, plays a key role in influencing flood events within the study area. Furthermore, the constricted artificial riverbed in the river's downstream sections, caused by agricultural and urban activities, disrupts the river's natural flow patterns and contributes to flooding incidents.

As reported by Skilodimou et al. (2019), the western, northern, and southwestern parts of the Peneus drainage basin include areas most susceptible to flooding, primarily along the mainstream of the Peneus drainage network. The moderate hazard zone is situated in the western and northern sections of the basin, while the low and very low hazard zones are found in the southern and eastern parts of the area (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. The flood hazard assessment map in the drainage basin of the Peneus River.

Land use changes in areas impacted by extensive fires have contributed to an increase in flood events. Additionally, the constricted artificial riverbed in the lower reaches of the Peneus River, resulting from agricultural land use and urban development, significantly disrupts the natural flow dynamics and exacerbates flooding.

Table 1 displays the percentage of area covered by each flood hazard zone for the Xerias, Phoenix, and Peneus drainage basins.

Table 1. The percentage of area for each flood hazard zone for the Xerias, Phoenix, and Peneus drainage basins.

Flood hazard zone	Xerias drainage basin	Phoenix drainage basin	Peneus drainage basin
	Area (%)		
Very low	9	38	8
Low	27	36	24
Moderate	40	16	39
High	15	8	20
Very high	9	2	9

In the Xerias drainage basin, the very high and high flood hazard zones cover a significant portion, making up about one-quarter of the basin. In comparison, the Phoenix drainage basin has a much smaller coverage, with these two zones spanning only 10% of the area. The Peneus drainage basin, however, has the largest extent, with the very high and high hazard zones covering approximately one-third of the basin.

Conclusions

The total number of past flood events across the drainage basins of the Xerias, Phoenix, and Peneus rivers amounts to twenty-nine. The northern and central areas of the Xerias and Phoenix drainage basins are the most flood-prone, while the western, northern, and southwestern regions of the Peneus drainage basin are particularly vulnerable to flooding. Among the three drainage basins, the Peneus drainage basin has the largest areas classified as very high and high flood hazard zones.

The gentle slopes and widespread urban development of the lowland areas in the Xerias drainage basin play a role in flooding. In the downstream sections of the Phoenix River drainage basin, the narrow artificial riverbed, shaped by agricultural and urban activities, also contributes to flooding. Changes in land use in regions affected by extensive fires have led to an increase in flooding events in the Peneus drainage basin.

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